

CALCIUM LOOPING TO DECARBONIZE CO₂-INTENSE INDUSTRIES WITH ADDED REVENUE STREAMS

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Abstract

Calcium Looping (CaL) is a competitive carbon capture (CC) technology due to the inherently efficient process combined with its offsetting revenue streams such as additional heat and/or power as well as calcined lime. CaL technology can be applied to virtually all carbon-intensive industries, including heat & power, cement plants as well as current and future iron- & steelmaking processes. Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW) is a global provider of solutions and services that drive the decarbonization of several industries. SFW has developed CC solutions since the late 2000s, including the CaL technology based on circulating fluidized beds (CFB). Now, we are extending the technology development to new applications, and we target commercial demonstration of SFW CaL+ with partnering customers for 2025-2027 (depending on the application case). In this conference we will outline and discuss the status of SFW CaL+ product development, related piloting and demonstration activities as well as the pathway towards commercialization of the technology.

1. Introduction

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), Carbon capture (CC) is an unavoidable climate mitigation tool to reach Net-Zero emissions by 2050. The accelerated deployment of CC projects by 2030 is essential in reaching that target. The market for CC solutions is promoted by several factors, including financial and technological aspects. In the first phase of market development the focus is on capturing CO₂ emissions from existing power and industrial plants, with over 85 % of all CO₂ emissions captured during this decade from existing plants retrofitted with CO₂ capture equipment. Of particular interest are the steel and cement sectors, which along with the chemical sector, emit ~ 60% of all global industrial CO₂ emissions (IPCC, 2023).

Irrespective of the selected technology, all CC solutions add costs due to reasons such as additional equipment, additional energy to operate, and added burdens related to the storage and/or utilization of the captured CO₂. Independent estimates suggest that the most cost-effective CC technologies, including calcium looping (CaL) based on circulating fluidized beds (CFB), could capture CO₂ from industrial sources for less than 60 EUR/t_{CO2}. This figure could be reduced even further to below 40 EUR/t_{CO2} if offsetting revenues are considered along with utilization of synergy effects, and optimized process integration. The CaL process requires oxygen, often considered to be supplied by a cryogenic air separation unit (ASU). In the current market, the oxygen could be supplied from the ever-growing fleet of electrolyser instead. Furthermore, the CaL process is in fact a net energy generator, thus enabling revenues via the sales of additional heat and/or power.

2. Calcium Looping Process Fundamentals

The CaL process decarbonizes flue gas (FG) by means of cyclic carbonation/calcination (see Eq. 1) of a Ca-based sorbent, e.g., natural, non-toxic limestone. The process fundamentals are shown in Figure 1. Accordingly, the circulating sorbent is exposed to cyclic carbonation-calcination conditions within carbonator and calciner, whereby CO₂ is separated from an FG stream and made available as a highly CO₂-enriched product gas. Typically, a CO₂ processing

unit (CPU) is needed for purification, compression and/or liquification of the CO₂ product gas according to the requirements set by the targeted CO₂ use/storage/transportation strategy.

Figure 1: CaL process fundamentals (a: Simplified process scheme, b: Carbonation-calcination equilibrium partial pressure of CO₂).

The heat required to run the CaL process is supplied via oxyfuel combustion in the CFB calciner. Thereby, the inherent fuel flexibility of CFBs allows for the utilization of various fuel candidates, including sustainably sourced bio-residues and/or waste-derived fuels. The oxygen can be provided either by an ASU or as by-product from electrolyzers.

To maintain the CO₂ absorption capacity of the sorbent, and to compensate for the loss of fine sorbent from the circulation loop, a continuous stream of fresh limestone make-up is fed to the process. Deactivated sorbent and fuel ashes, often referred to as “CaL purge”, are continuously discharged from the CaL process. As both reactors (carbonator and calciner) operate at relatively high temperature levels (~ 650 & 900 °C), the process excess heat can be efficiently recovered via a water/steam cycle. Alternatively, if suitable high-temperature heat sinks exist in the proximity of the CaL unit, direct heat integration scenarios can be implemented.

2. Calcium Looping Applications and Integration Synergies

The CaL process according to its basic process scheme (Fig. 1), is a multiproduct technology. In addition to the CO₂ captured from the industrial source, the process supplies additional process heat and/or power as well as calcined lime which represents a feedstock for clinker/cement manufacturing or other lime-based industries. Moreover, co-capture capabilities of acid gases within the CFB carbonator could potentially replace FG cleaning equipment within the host process. The high-temperature process heat from the CaL dual-CFB system is available at different process locations within carbonator and calciner. This allows to partially decouple the process sections that are most exposed to fuel impurities and the locations where high temperature heat is transferred. Moreover, the classical CFB combustion process has proven its dynamic flexibility in commercial installations which makes CFB-CaL also suitable for applications that require a transient flexibility from the CC system. Such requirements are exemplarily known from Electric Arc Furnace (EAF) and Argon Oxygen Decarburization (AOD) processes for the production of iron & steel.

The process concept and its integration approach into the respective host plant represents therefore one means to maximize process performance and synergy effects according to the case specific requirements. SFW CaL+ can be applied for CO₂ capture from point-source CO₂ emissions released from various industrial processes, including for instance cement, iron & steel, biomass fuelled power plants, waste incineration plants. The following section provides an overview on the application and synergies of the CaL process in hard-to-abate industrial sectors for the example of SFW CaL+ for the cement industry.

In 2020, the global production of cement was 4.2 billion tons. This has led to 2.7 billion tons of CO₂ emissions, which equals around 6% of global CO₂ emissions from energy and industrial processes. The CO₂ intensity of cement production is around 640 kg/t_{cement} (GCCA, 2022). Cement manufacturing is considered as a hard-to-abate sector as most of the CO₂ emissions

are process related. More specifically, approximately, 2/3 of total CO₂ emissions originates from the calcination of calcium carbonate as part of limestone, the major substance in the feedstock (raw meal) of cement. Formation of this CO₂ emission portion occurs during the processing from raw meal to clinker, the predecessor of cement.

Among the different technology options to decarbonize cement manufacturing, the CaL process is considered relevant due to the potential process synergies (Plaza, 2020). CaL can make cement plants self-sufficient in power production and turn them into sellers of firm decarbonized electricity even after considering the power consumption of the CaL plant, including carbon processing unit (CPU) and ASU (if applicable). The CaL purge may be either used to increase cement plant production capacity, or to replace limestone in the feedstock, i.e., in the raw meal.

Fig. 2 a) shows the “tail-end” configuration of SFW CaL+ for cement plants. Hereby, the integration level of the CC unit and the host process is low. The use of CaL purge as feedstock

Figure 2. Options to integrated SFW CaL+ into cement production, a) “Tail-end”, b) “Integrated”.

for cement manufacturing can be considered to either increase production capacity or the partly decarbonize feedstock via the supply of calcined lime. Operating the cement plant without operating the CO₂ capture system is therefore possible.

Fig. 2 b) shows the “integrated” configuration of SFW CaL+ for cement plants, according to which the capture of CO₂ via CaL and manufacturing of cement (clinker) are merged into one process via a shared calciner. Thereby, the process synergies are maximized, which leads to

a lower footprint of the CaL system along with improved key performance indicators. In case of retrofitting integrated SFW CaL+ to existing assets, the re-use of plant components could be considered to further reduce costs.

A recent estimate showed that for a “tail-end” scenario utilizing low-cost waste-derived fuel in the CaL calciner, the levelized cost of capture can be approximately 30 EUR/t_{CO2}, by monetizing only power revenues and even assuming no oxygen synergies in place (SFW, 2023).

3. Roadmap Towards SFW CaL+ Commercialization

Pilot-scale testing and demonstration are vital for the development of novel technologies. SFW has developed CC solutions since the late 2000s, including the CaL technology based on CFBs, developed jointly with CSIC/HUNOSA/ENDESA over the last 10+ years.

The CaL process based on CFBs has been demonstrated already in various pilot plants up to MW-scale, leading to a technology readiness level (TRL) between 6-7, depending on the application scenario in question. As of today, the three most relevant CFB-CaL pilot plants are listed below:

- 200 kW pilot plant at University of Stuttgart, Germany (Hornberger, 2020)
- 1.0 MW pilot plant at Technische Universität Darmstadt, Germany (Haaf, 2020), based on SFW technology
- 1.7 MW plant at La Pereda power plant, Spain (Arias, 2023; Fig. 3), based on SFW technology

Figure 3: “La Pereda” 1.7 MW CaL demonstration plant (La Pereda, Spain).

SFW recently joined forces with partnering organizations in the frame of two EU-funded research projects (CaLby2030 and HERCCULES) to bring the CFB-CaL technology towards commercialization (CaLby2030, 2022; HERCCULES, 2023). Both projects directly support SFW’s roadmap for commercialization of SFW CaL+ within the coming years. Focus lies on the development and demonstration of the CaL process for hard-to-abate sectors, namely cement, iron & steel, biomass combined heat and power (BioCHP) as well as waste-to-energy (WtE). As part of these two projects, two new CFB-CaL pilot plants are designed by SFW, which will be erected and tested. The new pilot plants will be specifically designed to

demonstrate the CaL process under the conditions relevant for iron & steel industrial sectors (Kettunen, 2024) and WtE (HERCCULES, 2023). Moreover, the existing pilots in Stuttgart and La Pereda will be upgraded for conditions relevant to cement and Bio-CHP applications.

In addition to the extensive test program in the TRL 6-7 pilot plants as listed above, SFW is exploiting its vast in-house expertise, dimensioning tools and databases generated from more than 850 commercial FB combustors and gasifiers, totaling over 40 GW_e of installed power capacity (SFW, 2024). As an example of such expertise, Fig 4 shows the SFW Biomass CFB evolution, from 0.5 MW pilot-scale up to 300 MW_e CFB size class.

Figure 4: SFW Biomass CFB evolution (unit size in MW_e).

Further acceleration in SFW CaL+ technology demonstration is related to similarities in the mode of combustion within the CaL calciner. SFW demonstrated already CFB oxyfuel combustion in 30 MW_{th} during the 2010s at the Fundacion Ciudad de la Energia (CIUDEN, Spain), accumulating thousands of operational hours under various conditions. Based on the demonstration activities, commercial development with partners led to the completion of FEED activities and development of a readily available 300 MW_e CFB Oxyfuel power plant design (Eriksson, 2013). Now, those experiences allow us to upscale more rapidly the SFW CaL+ technology, since in both processes (CaL calciner, oxyfuel boiler) the fuel is combusted in a CFB oxyfuel environment.

4. Conclusion

The implementation of CC technologies as a climate mitigation tool is required to reach Net-Zero emissions by 2050. The accelerated deployment of CC projects by 2030, is essential in reaching that target. Sumitomo SHI FW (SFW) – as a technology forerunner – is currently expanding the SFW CaL+ technology demonstration to new applications, including Bio-CHP, WtE, cement and steel. Such demonstration is due in relevant industrial environments, in collaboration with commercial partners, and targeting commercial readiness in 2025-2027, depending on the application.

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